

Editorial

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Intrusion Detection System in Cloud Computing: A Review

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Abstract: With greater flexibility and less infrastructure investment, cloud computing offers end customers scalable, virtualised on-demand services. These services are offered via the Internet while adhering to accepted networking protocols, standards, and file formats. Due to its distributed and scalable nature, cloud computing is currently preferred by the majority of IT firms. However, potential attackers for cyber threats are paying close attention to its flexible and open architecture. The Intrusion Detection System (IDS) is crucial in this situation for keeping an eye on hostile activity in cloud-based systems. This paper systematically reviews the existing methods for detecting intrusions based on various techniques and methods such as traditional techniques and soft computing methods.

Key Words: Intrusion detection system, cloud computing, cloud-based IDS, Signature IDS, Anomaly IDS, Hybrid IDS

I. INTRODUCTION

With the widespread increase in technological advancement and the use of the internet, computing accessories and resources have become more readily available, more powerful, more resourceful, more common, and more accessible than ever before. This technological advancement has enabled connectivity, communication, collaboration, and access to remote devices. Information storage and accessibility are now easily possible with the use of computer systems, mobile devices, and other electronic devices (Jang-Jaccard *et al.*, 2013). Hence, individuals, business owners, firms, organisations, and government agencies are now embracing this fast-evolving digital infrastructure without considering the vulnerabilities it exhibits and sharing their

data and information without any thought of loss of privacy. However, as technology advances, new security threats and challenges regarding safety, trust, availability, and reliability emerge. Because cloud computing technology is internet-based, there is a high risk of intrusion and malicious attacks exploiting new vulnerabilities created by the transition from the common and traditional method of storing, processing, and accessing information, data, and communication to the new environment (Kosamkar, 2016; Sadiku *et al.*, 2022). Studies have shown that the innovation of many existing technologies, such as web services, web browsers, and virtualisation, has contributed to the development of cloud-based systems. Hence, any intrusions, threats, and attacks associated with these technologies also affect the cloud; they can even have a more dangerous effect in this environment (Hashizume *et al.*, 2013).

As a result, "cloud computing" can be defined as "an emerging technology that provides on-demand computing resources and services via the internet" (Samreen & Zaidi, 2012). That is, an Internet-based platform for data processing, storage, and sharing resources such as infrastructure, software, applications, and business processes (Sadiku *et al.*, 2022; Suthar, 2017). The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) proposed a definition of cloud computing in its NIST Special Publication 800-145 as "a model for enabling ubiquitous, convenient, on-demand network access to a shared pool of configurable computing resources that can be rapidly provisioned and released with minimal management effort or service provider interaction" (Mell & Grance, 2011). This cloud model is composed of five essential characteristics, three service models, and four deployment models.

Figure 1: Architecture of Cloud Computing (MEGATEK ICT Academy, 2020)

In today's world, it is almost impossible to ponder the digital evolution of businesses and organisations without mentioning cloud computing technologies (Chaudhary, 2020). Cloud computing possesses some features that differentiate it from traditional web services. Some of these features are multitenancy, resource pooling, virtualisation, on-demand self-service, elasticity, automatic or easy resource deployment, and metered billing. When compared to using a typical web service provider, all of these enable cloud computing to provide users with more cost savings, automation, and flexibility. Communication in cloud computing technology can be separated into two sections: the front end and the back end. The client, or computer user, serves as the front end of the system, and the cloud is responsible for its back end (Ade, 2020; Odun-Ayo *et al.*, 2018). Based on the interface of the cloud services, the personal computer requires access to the coordination of cloud computing. Computers, a storage system, and servers make up the back-end infrastructure, which in turn generates the dedicated servers and cloud services required for these applications (Dinh *et al.*, 2013; Mansouri *et al.*, 2020; Sunyaev, 2020).

In cloud computing technology, computing resources are shared rather than having a local server or personal devices to handle applications. In other words, it enables consumers and businesses to use applications without installing them and to access their files from any computer or electronic device with internet access (Thakur *et al.*, 2017). In general, cloud computing technology is capable of delivering three types of services and four deployment models. Service delivery models include:

1. Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS): Examples include Digital Ocean, Linode, Rackspace, and Amazon.
2. Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS): These include operating systems and developer platforms. OpenShift for the Google App Engine.
3. Software (apps) as a service (SaaS): For instance, GoToMeeting, Cisco Webx, Zoom, Drive, and Office 365.

Deployment models include public, private, community, and hybrid. Each of these models has different features, and the deployment model depends on the cloud user objectives. Before accepting a model deployment, the user is encouraged to review the security, reliability, and performance issues associated with the models (Mansouri *et al.*, 2020; Odun-Ayo *et al.*, 2018).

With the facts established and known that, in today's world, cloud computing is a technology that has been accepted and used by many, it is therefore vulnerable to various intrusions, attacks, and anomalies. As a result, the security of cloud systems is critical in protecting the data source from external and internal intruders and attacks. As a result, many security tools and techniques have been proposed to secure and prevent cloud attacks. One of these methods is intrusion detection systems (Krishnan, 2017) but in reality, there are various inadequacies and limitations to the existing traditional IDS methods and techniques used in detecting intrusion in cloud-based environments due to the nature of the cloud technology. Therefore, this necessitates the development of a new cloud-based IDS that can meet its security needs.

The focus of this paper is to review the various techniques for detecting intrusion in a cloud computing environment. This paper is organised as follows: Section 2 presents general background knowledge of intrusion and intrusion detection systems in cloud environments, and Section 3 presents the existing works. The conclusion is provided in the final section.

II. INTRUSIONS IN THE CLOUD

Research on cloud security is ongoing, and numerous solutions have been put forth and improved. An intrusion is now a crucial area of cybersecurity data analytics and is defined as any action intended to compromise the security, confidentiality, integrity, or availability of a system, network or cloud (CIA), including any internet attack, attempts by authorised users to gain more access to the system, or by authorised users who abuse their access (Lata & Singh, 2022; Liu *et al.*, 2022; Modi *et al.*, 2013). Any of the following could constitute an intrusion:

1. Trojans, worms, and viruses that replicate in the network.
2. Sending specially designed packets to take advantage of any flaws.
3. Attacks that would render the services inoperable even for loyal customers.

Utilising a cloud-based intrusion detection system is one of the effective methods to stop such attempts (Elmasry *et al.*, 2021). In reality, the most known intrusions that affect the confidentiality, integrity, or availability of cloud services include the following.

A. Insider attack

This frequently occurs when authorised users with access to an organisation's networks, systems, and data attempt to get and abuse the rights that have been or have not been legally granted to them. Since insiders could disclose information to adversaries, this attack is strongly tied to trust, and with this, the privacy of cloud users has been violated by this attack (Mehmood *et al.*, 2013).

B. Attacks via backdoor channels

By taking advantage of this passive assault, hackers can breach the privacy of user information and get remote access to compromised workstations. To take over the victim's resources and use them as zombies in a DDoS assault, hackers can use backdoor channels (Modi *et al.*, 2013). The secrecy and accessibility of cloud users are the targets of this attack. Any mechanism by which authorised or unauthorised users can go beyond standard security precautions and obtain root access to take over the victim's resources and use them as zombies in a DDoS assault the secrecy and accessibility of cloud users are the targets of this attack. There are numerous methods for executing backdoor threats (Doan *et al.*, 2021; Li *et al.*, 2021, 2022; Nguyen & Tran, 2020). They include:

1. Taking advantage of security system flaws that permit unauthorised access to the system or data.
2. Putting malware on a machine that grants the attacker access to it.
3. Gaining access to systems using credentials that have been stolen or cracked.
4. By the covert insertion of messages that grant the attacker power over the systems or users into communications between systems or users.

C. Hypervisor or Virtual Machine Attacks

An attacker might take over the virtual machines by getting access to the hypervisor. SubVirt, BLUEPILL and DKSM are the most frequent assaults on the virtual layer that provide hackers access to the host through the hypervisor (Bahram *et al.*, 2010; Khairkar *et al.*, 2013; King *et al.*, 2006). Attackers target zero-day vulnerabilities in virtual machines to get access to them before the developers are aware of such exploits. Numerous websites running on virtual servers were harmed because of a zero-day vulnerability in the HyperVM application being exploited (Mehmood *et al.*, 2013).

D. Denial of Service (DoS) attack

To overwhelm the available resources, the attacker takes advantage of zombies to transmit a lot of network packets. As a result, authorised users are prevented from using the services provided online. DoS attacks—which involve sending a large number of requests to reach VMs through zombies in a cloud environment—are what render those VMs unavailable to authorised users (Modi *et al.*, 2013). The accessibility of cloud resources is the objective of this assault.

E. Port Scanning

Port scanning can be used by attackers to gather a list of blocked, open, and unfiltered ports from which they can launch attacks against services using those open ports. SYN scanning, ACK scanning, TCP scanning, FIN scanning, UDP scanning, and other port scanning techniques are among them. Port scanning is a technique that attackers can employ to locate open ports in a cloud environment, after which they can focus on the services that are using them. This assault can result in the loss of integrity and secrecy on the cloud (Modi *et al.*, 2013).

F. User-to-root attacks (U2R)

By using password sniffing, the attacker can access a valid user's account and utilise system weaknesses to get root access. Root shells can be created by utilising buffer overflows from a root-level process. In a cloud situation, an attacker gains access to legitimate user instances before gaining root rights on the host or virtual machines. The integrity of cloud-based systems has been violated by this attack (Modi *et al.*, 2013).

III. INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEMS

This section provides a quick review of the research that has been done on cloud-based IDS. An intrusion detection system is a software system or hardware device that scans all incoming and outgoing network traffic for unusual patterns that can point to a security breach in a network or system. The IDS scans traffic for signatures that correspond to recognised intrusion patterns and issues an alert when a match is discovered (Farsole *et al.*, 2010; Mukhopadhyay & Nath, 2014; Patil *et al.*, 2018). To keep an eye on suspicious traffic coming from outside or inside the network, the IDS is installed either inside or outside the firewall, depending on the traffic that has to be watched. IDS has many ways of working, but one of them is that it collects and examines data from a computer or a network to find any potential breaches of the security policy, including illegal access or misuse. An IDS analyses traffic for potential intrusions and issues a warning when such intrusions are found.

A. Cloud-based intrusion detection using kernel fuzzy clustering and optimal type-2 fuzzy neural network

Because people access cloud data over the Internet, the information there is vulnerable to numerous invasions. In the cloud, intrusion detection is thought to be a major problem. The currently available algorithms can identify well-known assaults but struggle to identify less frequent ones. The authors proposed an innovative intrusion detection system (IDS) in the cloud that combines kernel fuzzy c-means clustering (KFCM) and an ideal type-2 fuzzy neural network to address this problem (OT2FNN). To do this, we use the Lion optimisation algorithm (LOA) for weight optimisation to select the T2FNN parameters in the best possible way (Srilatha & Shyam, 2021).

B. Cloud Intrusion Detection System Using Fuzzy Clustering and Artificial Neural Network

An intrusion detection system (IDS) is a security layer that monitors systems for suspicious activity and sends out notifications when it is discovered. Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) are capable of detecting system intrusions, although there is a slight issue with ANN's lack of detection precision for infrequent attacks and stability. To solve the problem, The authors chose to adopt the FC-ANN strategy, which is based on fuzzy clusters and artificial neural networks. The general process for FC-ANN is as follows: various training subsets are first created using the fuzzy clustering technique. Different ANN models are then trained to create various base models using various training subsets (Chormale & Ghatule, 2020).

C. Application of Deep Learning Technique in an Intrusion Detection System

In this study, a hybrid network-based Intrusion Detection System (IDS) is employed to detect network intrusions using deep learning techniques. On the NSL-KDD and ISCXIDS 2012 datasets, the effectiveness of the suggested technique is assessed. Wireshark was used to do traffic visual analysis, and experiments were conducted to demonstrate the superiority of the suggested approach over the various base models (Saraeian & Golchi, 2020).

D. Attacks and Intrusion Detection in Cloud Computing Using Neural Networks and Particle Swarm Optimisation Algorithms

Cloud computing has gained popularity among users in businesses and organisations nowadays. The two main problems facing cloud service providers and their clients are security and efficiency. Cloud-based services come with security threats since cloud computing is a virtual pool of resources offered in an open environment (the Internet). One of the main issues for cloud service providers and users alike is the detection of intrusions and attacks by unauthorised users. In the current study, intrusion and assault detection were accomplished using artificial intelligence approaches, such as the MLP Neural Network and particle swarm optimisation algorithms. Datasets for NSL-KDD and KDD-CUP were used to test the approaches (Saljoughi *et al.*, 2017).

E. Network Intrusion Detection Method Combining CNN and BiLSTM in Cloud Computing Environment

In this paper, a CNN-Bi LSTM and C5.0-based network intrusion detection system is proposed. First, the original data set is processed using procedures including data

cleaning, data extraction, and data mapping before the data extraction method, SamExtract, is used to turn multiple traffic samples into grayscale images. Second, to make up for the insufficient extraction of local features, local parallel features are retrieved by CNN. To better understand the impact of the attributes before and after each attribute point in the sequence data, and to reduce FA, utilise bi-LSTM to extract long-distance-dependent features (Gao, 2022).

F. Application of data mining technology in detecting network intrusion and security maintenance

To detect network intrusion and maintain security, this work suggests an enhanced k-means algorithm and an improved *a priori* algorithm used in data mining technologies. The trial with the enhanced algorithms was carried out in this work using the traditional KDDCUP99 dataset. Comparisons are made between the algorithm's detection rate and false alarm rate and the experimental data from before the improvement. In terms of several simulation characteristics, such as average time, false alarm rate, absolute error, and accuracy value, the results of the proposed algorithms are examined. The findings demonstrate that the enhanced algorithm improves the detection model's designed detection efficiency and accuracy (Zhu *et al.*, 2021).

G. Intrusion Detection System with Snort in Cloud Computing: Advanced IDS

To guard against malicious packets, a Snort-based intrusion detection system was introduced in this work. Snort in IDS is efficient and more secure in identifying intrusions and has proven to be more advantageous to the user or organisations because security in cloud computing is essential to storing and moving the data over the internet. Data packets are more securely protected by Snort since they are thoroughly processed by network layer protocols (Mishra *et al.*, 2016; Modi *et al.*, 2012).

H. A fingerprinting system calls approach for intrusion detection in a cloud environment

Cloud-based systems are vulnerable to a wide range of assaults because of their distributed nature, with VM-based attacks being the most prevalent. Intrusion Detection System (IDS), which is used to monitor network traffic and policy breaches from unauthorised users, is necessary to defend against these attacks. Anomaly Detection is a method of Intrusion Detection that uses system activity monitoring to identify patterns that deviate from expected behaviour to uncover intrusions. This study presents a method for detecting anomalies in cloud environments that are based on system call sequence analysis from the virtual machines to the hypervisor (Gupta *et al.*, 2012).

IV. INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEMS IN THE CLOUD

Intrusion detection systems have become an important aspect of security measures to shield and protect computer resources and the entire network from any activities that are suspicious and dangerous to the computer systems. Hence, an intrusion detection system may be a hardware or software program that tracks, monitors, analyses, and reacts to hostile behaviour occurring on a computer system or network for indications of potential security policy violations (Khairkar *et al.*, 2013). If such activity is found, it issues a warning alarm and sends notifications to the system administrator. However, the

performance of the system may be impacted if the warning alerts sent by the IDS are false alarms or irrelevant to the real breach. IDS must be built so that it can identify false alarms in addition to intrusions.

A strong cloud security strategy must include cloud IDS as a key component. A cloud intrusion detection system is an IDS that has been built in a cloud-native form factor to monitor both on-premises and cloud-based assets as part of a cloud-delivered security strategy or for the protection of cloud-based resources under an IaaS security model (Kene & Theng, 2015; Lata & Singh, 2022). To detect and stop attacks that come from both within the cloud itself and from users accessing cloud technology from various locations via the Internet, a proper defence strategy in the cloud needs to be properly distributed.

As a result, IDS should be designed and implemented in such a way that they can detect all attacks connected to clouds across the entire cloud network with as few false alarms as possible. A cloud intrusion detection system (IDS) is essential for intrusion detection and incident response in cloud-based technology (Rani & Gagandeep, 2022). Key characteristics of a cloud IDS include (Kene & Theng, 2015; Lata & Singh, 2022):

1. Integrated Security: IDS capability is frequently included in other security products, including security gateways for cloud-native environments, next-generation FWaaS, SSE, and SASE. This security integration allows automatic threat detection and response while also streamlining security administration.
2. Threat Detection: An intrusion detection system's main objective is to detect threats. To find possible threats and produce alerts, an intrusion detection system may employ a range of various processes (machine learning, signature detection, anomaly detection, etc.).
3. Easy Installation: Cloud intrusion detection systems can be set up either utilising a service-based architecture or as virtual appliances. As a result, it is easy to roll out new solutions quickly to address shifting business needs.

An organisation can use a cloud IDS to efficiently and scalably identify potential threats to their cloud-based deployments. An organisation can gain from using cloud IDS in the following ways:

1. Cloud protection: Businesses are increasingly processing and storing data on cloud infrastructure. A corporation's security team may discover and address any threats to its cloud-based infrastructure because of a cloud IDS (Kene & Theng, 2015; Lata & Singh, 2022).
2. Flexibility: A cloud-based virtualised architecture that is shared by an IDS also has this benefit. Because the solution is built as a virtualised appliance or is used in a service-based paradigm, businesses can deploy, modify, or discontinue security monitoring capabilities as needed to meet shifting business needs.
3. Remote Access Support: Businesses are encouraging employees to work remotely more and more, and these remote employees need access to corporate cloud services. IDS can be used as a part of a SASE solution, which combines an IDS and secures remote access functionality into a single, cohesive package.
4. Managed Security: Cloud intrusion detection could be used with a service-based product like SASE or firewall as a service (FWaaS). This makes it possible for a

company to delegate to their security service provider the duties and costs associated with security management.

5. Scalability: Cloud-native IDS provides the scalability benefits of the cloud-based architecture. With the aid of a cloud IDS, an organisation's security monitoring capabilities may scale to meet demand and keep up with the expansion of cloud-based services.

A. Types of cloud-based IDS

Intrusion detection systems (IDSs), which are security technologies, are used to identify suspicious or malicious activities by both internal and external intruders. Such intrusive acts are seen as odd and against the security guidelines of the system. The IDS should sound an alarm when it detects these. This security concept is an active monitoring and defence solution that guards vital IT infrastructure against shady activities. IDS usage has expanded significantly because of the large number of data points and increasingly complicated system threats. Traditional IDS approaches do not meet cloud needs because most of the business and IT sectors are migrating toward decentralised architectures like cloud computing. IDS can be classified into four deployment categories in a cloud computing environment, (Rani & Gagandeep, 2022), as shown in Figure 2.

1. Host-based IDS (HIDS): It acquires and analyses data from a particular host to detect intrusive events. The data may be found in system logs or operating system audit trails. When a system or application behaves differently, HIDS analyses the data and alerts network management that the system is being attacked (Vieira *et al.*, 2010; Zouhair *et al.*, 2018). The effectiveness of HIDS can be improved by identifying the characteristics that provide it with additional information for detection (Mehmood *et al.*, 2013).
2. Hypervisor-based: A framework for communication across VMs is provided by the hypervisor. IDSs based on

hypervisors are installed at the hypervisor layer. It helps in the assessment of already-available information for the detection of unexpected behaviour. Information is reliant on communication at many different levels, including communication inside the virtual network created on a hypervisor, between VMs, and between VMs (Bharadwaja *et al.*, 2011; Modi *et al.*, 2013). Therefore, HCIDS examines system metrics for cloud instances directly from the hypervisor to search for probable patterns of misuse (Mehmood *et al.*, 2013).

3. Network-based IDS (NIDS): All network traffic is recorded and examined by NIDS to spot potential intrusions like port scanning and DoS attacks, among other things. NIDS typically performs intrusion detection when capturing network packets by processing the IP and transport layer headers (Gao, 2022; Hsu *et al.*, 2019; Sakr *et al.*, 2019). To locate intrusions, it uses anomaly-based and signature-based detection methodologies (Mehmood *et al.*, 2013). Network intrusion detection systems (NIDS) collect network packets and look for connections to well-known attack signatures, or they match real-time user behaviour to profiles that are already known about them (Chung *et al.*, 2013).
4. Distributed IDS (DIDS): It consists of multiple IDSs over a large network, all of which communicate with each other, or with a central server that facilitates advanced network monitoring, incident analysis, and instant attack data. By having these cooperative agents distributed across a network, incident analysts, network operations, and security personnel can get a broader view of what is occurring on the network (Kumar *et al.*, 2022). DIDS allows for efficient management of its incident analysis resources by centralizing its attack records and giving an analyst a quick and easy way to spot new trends and patterns and identify threats to the network across multiple network segments (Idhammad *et al.*, 2018).

Figure 2: Deployment Techniques (Saljoughi *et al.*, 2017)

Table 1. The Summary of Deployment Techniques in Intrusion Detection Systems

IDS	Characteristic	Limitation	Positioning in Cloud	Deployment and monitoring authority
HIDS	Detect intrusions by keeping an eye on the file system, system calls, or network activity of the host. No additional hardware is needed.	Installation of the host, hypervisor, or virtual machine software is required on each system. It can only keep track of attacks on hosts where it is installed.	On every host, hypervisor, or VM system	Cloud Users on VMs. Cloud provider on the hypervisor.
NIDS	Detect intrusions by keeping an eye on network activity. Only the underlying network needs to be installed. Multiple systems can be monitored simultaneously.	It only aids in detecting external intruders. it is challenging to identify network intrusions in virtual networks. it is difficult to detect intrusions from encrypted communications.	Either in a virtual or external network	Cloud service
Hypervisor	It enables users to track and examine communications within the hypervisor-based virtual network, between VMs, and between the hypervisor and a VM.	New and challenging to comprehend	The hypervisor	Cloud service
DIDS	utilises traits from both NIDS and HIDS and gains advantages from each of them as a result.	Expensive communication and processing costs. Difficult to manage in a centralised DIDS.	External network, on a host, a hypervisor, or a virtual machine.	Cloud users on VMs. In other cases: cloud service provider

Figure 3: Detection Techniques (Saljoughi *et al.*, 2017)

B. Techniques for detecting an intrusion.

In cloud environments, different methods and techniques for detecting intrusion are used, such as anomaly-based, signature-based, or a combination of both.

1. Signature-based intrusion detection techniques

The signature-based intrusion detection system (IDS) will monitor network traffic packets and compare them to a database of known malicious threat signatures, or rules. Since they do not need to learn the environment, signature-based techniques are simple to deploy and work by merely searching, inspecting, and comparing the contents of captured network packets for known threat signatures (Kene

& Theng, 2015). Additionally, it contrasts behaviour signatures with those that are permitted. The system calls are also examined using a signature-based methodology for known risks. payload When used with known attacks and violations, the signature-based approach is quite effective, but unless it is updated with new signatures, it cannot identify new assaults (Mudzingwa & Agrawal, 2012). Attackers can easily get around signature-based detection systems by modifying known attacks and aiming for systems that have not been updated with fresh signatures that identify the alteration.

Figure 4: Signature-Based Methodology Architecture (Mudzingwa & Agrawal, 2012)

Figure 5: Anomaly-Based Methodology Architecture (Mudzingwa & Agrawal, 2012)

2. Anomaly-based intrusion detection techniques

Anomaly-Based Intrusion Detection System, also known as behaviour-based, monitors network traffic and compares it to the expected flow. Anomalous activity is alerted to the administrator or user by any deviation from typical traffic. Given that not all anomalies are intrusions, the rate of false positives is considerable. These IDS require system

administrators to distinguish between genuine attacks and false positives due to the possibility of many deviations in incoming traffic packets and known patterns. By contrasting observed activity with a reference profile, anomaly-based analysis analyses data. The baseline profile, which represents the monitored system's learned typical behaviour, is created during the learning phase, during which the IDS learns the

environment and creates a typical profile for the monitored system. Networks, people, and systems can all be parts of this ecosystem, and the anomaly itself may be static or dynamic. A dynamic profile varies as the systems being monitored develop, while a fixed profile remains constant after it has been set. Zero-day assaults on the environment can be found using anomaly-based approaches without the need for system updates (Mudzingwa & Agrawal, 2012). Three general methods, statistical anomaly detection, knowledge/data mining, and machine learning or deep learning, are used by anomalous intrusion detection methodologies to find anomalies. With the level at which the intruders are operating, a high-intelligence IDS is needed to protect the cloud environment.

The introduction of soft computing approaches is appealing to use in intrusion detection because of their capacity to deal with ambiguous and incomplete data (Modi *et al.*, 2012). To increase the effectiveness and detection accuracy of signature-based IDS or anomaly detection-based IDS, a variety of soft computing techniques, including Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Fuzzy Logic, Association Rule Mining, Support Vector Machines (SVM), Genetic Algorithms (GA), etc., are used.

- **Artificial Neural Network (ANN):** ANNs are used for intrusion detection to generalise information from sparse data and to categorise data as either normal or intrusive. The following are the ANN kinds that are utilised in IDS: Multi-Layer Feed-Forward (MLFF) neural networks, Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), and Back Propagation (BP). Unstructured network data can be effectively handled by ANN-based IDS. The number of hidden layers and the ANN training phase determine the efficacy of this approach's intrusion detection (Modi *et al.*, 2012). To learn ANN effectively, though, additional training samples and time are needed. Since a speedy intrusion detection technique is needed for cloud intrusion detection, using just ANN-based IDS is not a viable option.

- **Support Vector Machines (SVM):** For binary classification, the SVM is already regarded as the top learning method. The SVM has been successfully used in a range of pattern recognition applications. It is a sort of pattern classifier that was initially based on a statistical learning technique for classification and regression with a variety of kernel functions. It has recently been used in information security for intrusion detection. Because of their high generalisability and capacity to escape the "dimensionality curse," support vector machines have emerged as one of the most widely used methods for anomaly intrusion detection (Jha & Ragha, 2013).
- **Genetic Algorithms (GA):** Another machine learning strategy built on the fundamentals of evolutionary computation is genetic algorithms. They combine the ideas of Darwin's theory and natural selection to produce a set of guidelines that may be used to categorise incursions on a testing set. The use of GAs in intrusion detection has been studied by researchers (Goyal *et al.*, 2011).

3. Hybrid-based intrusion detection techniques

This method combines anomaly-based and signature-based detection methods to find intrusions more rapidly and accurately than either method by itself. A hybrid approach takes advantage of the best features of both; it uses the misuse and anomaly approaches, respectively, to identify known and unknown dangers. Using a variety of soft computing techniques, it might be feasible to simultaneously identify any type of assault. The authors used signature-based techniques with fuzzy genetic algorithms to discriminate between external and internal threats. Figure 5 provides a general overview of a hybrid-based methodology that combines three distinct methodologies (Mudzingwa & Agrawal, 2012). The first methodology analyses the monitored environment before passing it on to the second and third methodologies. An improved system results from this.

Figure 6: Hybrid-based methodology architecture (Mudzingwa & Agrawal, 2012)

C. Analysis of related cloud-based intrusion detection systems (CIDS)

In this section, we will discuss different CIDS and categorise them into three groups according to the intrusion detection method that each system employs. The three types are hybrid, anomaly-based, and signature-based.

1. Signature-based IDS

From the existing research based on signature IDS, to combat DoS and DDoS attacks, the authors suggested and modelled an IDS that functions cooperatively (Lo *et al.*, 2010). It consists of four parts, each having a distinct function. By capturing and examining network packets, the first one carries out intrusion detection. It immediately discards the packets that show a correlation with the block table rules, or else it forwards the anomalous packets that don't match these criteria to the alert clustering component, which determines the alert level of the received suspicious packet. The third element suppresses intrusion packets and notifies other IDS. The fourth part compiles warnings from other IDS and conducts a majority vote to decide on a packet. By implementing the suggested IDS, we can defend the system against single-point-of-failure attacks. However, because it uses signature-based detection approaches to find intrusions, it cannot detect unidentified attacks.

To identify denial-of-service (DoS) attacks on virtual SIP-based hosts, Mazzariello *et al.* (2010) examined the deployment of an intrusion detection system (IDS) at various locations within the cloud. The trials were carried out by the authors using Eucalyptus as a cloud and Snort as a network-based IDS. Eight virtual machines are being hosted by two of the six physical machines. There are two security groups set up, each with a SIP server, an Apache web server, and several RTP-based agents. To create background traffic, utilise distributed internet traffic generator (D-ITG). The SIP flood traffic is created using the "Invite Flood" program. The authors considered two scenarios to evaluate the IDS performance dependent on its cloud location. Findings from the assessment show that a single IDS instance placed close to the Cloud Controller (CC) will significantly increase the load on the CC when it comes to detecting DoS assaults. On the other hand, the deployment of a separate IDS instance at each virtual machine only affects the CPU burden of the attacked VM and has little to no effect on the other VMs. The suggested method relies on signatures and cannot identify unidentified attacks.

Another study by Bakshi and Dujodwala (2010) has proposed and implemented a distributed denial of service (DDoS) attack detection solution. Installing an IDS (such as Snort) on a virtual switch will enable the logging of incoming and outgoing traffic for auditing purposes into a database. The IDS detects specific threats (based on rules) in real-time by examining network packets. If IDS notices a lot of packets coming from a certain IP address (a DDoS attack), it notifies the virtual server, which bans the IP addresses of all the zombies in the botnet. The virtual server also updates routing tables and transfers the attacked apps to virtual machines (VMs) located in a different datacenter.

2. Anomaly-based IDS

An intrusion prevention system with autonomous agents has been presented by Patel *et al.* (2010). The method of detection is based on anomalies. Autonomous sensors are

used to keep an eye on network activity and system activity to spot suspicious events (such as system calls, file access, and changes). The system is capable of self-management with minimal human involvement, and the agents can be changed in-flight without having to restart them. The prevention system manages these agents by giving them high-level orders, including the provision of rules to stop an impending attack before it occurs based on risk analysis and risk appraisal. The necessary features are accomplished via a tiered management paradigm. There are seven layers: resource managers, knowledge and learning managers, risk managers, autonomous element managers, autonomous coordinators, and an integrated interface.

According to the degree of user abnormality, Lee *et al.* (2011) have presented a novel method to discover intrusions for efficient resource use. The authentication, authorisation, and accounting (AAA) module of the suggested system is a crucial component. When a user tries to use cloud services, a AAA module-based authentication procedure is applied. After successful authentication, the user's anomaly level—which is based on current database information about the user—is sent to the user. In light of the user's level of abnormality, AAA selects the appropriate IDS with the appropriate security level. The host operating system (OS) is configured with the selected IDS, and AAA requests that it assign the user's guest OS. When a guest OS is assigned to a user, a connection is made between the guest OS and the user's data in the storage centre. IDS has three different security levels: high, which employs all known attack patterns as well as some anomaly techniques when extra security is needed; medium, which provides a moderate level of security using all known attack patterns; and low, which employs a subset of known attack patterns that are particularly risky, common, and seriously damaging to systems. As a result, the suggested method provides speedy attack detection and enables the assignment of many guest OSs because medium- and low-level IDS have low resource needs.

The Virtual Machine Monitor (VMM) has been presented as a method for identifying intrusions in a virtualised environment (Bharadwaja *et al.*, 2011). Every VMM has the "Collabra" system, which acts as a link between Dom0 of the Xen-based virtual network and the VMM. It maintains track of and checks for anomalies in hyper-calls made to VMM by guest virtual machines (VMs). The use of anomaly-based detection is made necessary by the lack of well-known hyper-call attacks that can be utilised as signatures. As a result, it can effectively detect unidentified attacks. The system functions cooperatively because it can communicate with every copy of itself that is installed on different VMMs. Logical domain channels (LDC) are utilised as soon as an intrusion is found to notify other instances of the attack's features and to seek the sanitisation of the specific VMM. The hyper-calls are split into normal and abnormal groups based on a threshold value. One of the two primary security features provided by the Collabra system is the hyper-call integrity check, which performs cross-verification for each hyper-call started by a guest VM based on a message authentication code (MAC) and a designated policy for that call. With the aid of the MAC, a network of virtual machines running on a hypervisor can be maintained securely. access to the hyper-call origin where the admin version of Collabra may identify the origin of approved hyper-calls. When a

guest VM hyper-call originates from a website other than an authorised application, it is flagged as untrusted, and the associated Collabra instance is informed of the details of the call. The proposed method enables rapid detection of coordinated and distributed attacks at the hypervisor layer.

3. Hybrid IDS

To defend against both known and unknown attacks, Modi *et al.* (2012) have created and deployed a network IDS that uses Snort to identify known attacks and a Bayesian classifier to detect unknown attacks. The primary components of the suggested system are as follows:

During packet preprocessing, information from network packets that is unrelated to detection is removed. To assess if a packet is normal or an intrusion, the analyser uses a signature-based or anomaly-based detection method. If the packet is an intrusion, it is recorded using a Bayesian classifier, Snort, and Alert Log. Other servers' NIDS receives alert logs, notifies them, and keeps them on their systems. In the knowledge base and behaviour base, respectively, of the storage module are stored the rules of known attacks and frequent or invasive network events. Initially, Snort is used to identify intrusions when network packets are collected and intrusion events are stored in a database of alerts. Preprocessing non-intrusion packets, using a Bayesian classifier to determine whether they should be classified as intrusions or normal while considering the behaviour base, and finally logging the determined intrusions into an alert database are the subsequent steps in anomaly detection. The NIDS placed on each server can more quickly identify unknown threats by adding alarms to their knowledge base. Because anomaly detection only detects unidentified assaults, this method uses it after signature-based detection to speed up detection. Moreover, the detection rate is raised by sending alerts to other NIDS placed in a cloud environment.

Vieira *et al.* (2010) have proposed an Intrusion Detection System for Grid and Cloud Computing (GCCIDS) that operates at the middleware layer and may identify intrusions by combining knowledge-based and behaviour-based techniques. This system's nodes can detect intrusions and send out alerts to other nodes. As a result, the intrusion detection process develops cooperatively. The node, which contains resources that middleware can access equally, the service, which facilitates communication, and the event auditor, which compiles data from various sources, such as the service, the log system, and node messages, are the other two main components of the proposed architecture, in addition to the IDS service. The fourth element is the storage service, which holds the data that the IDS service will be evaluating. The authors evaluated the behaviour-based system by measuring false positives and false negatives, and they concluded that when the same amount of data is used as input, false negatives are always bigger than false positives. However, they found that if only a few comparison criteria are used, it is possible to monitor traffic in real-time using the knowledge-based system when employing audit data from communication and log systems (Vieira *et al.*, 2010). The authors have not yet released implementation details but intend to in their further work.

Shelke *et al.* (2012) have suggested a multi-threaded NIDS to handle the problem of Cross-Site Scripting (XSS) and

DDoS attacks. Three components make up the proposed NIDS, each of which serves a specific purpose: The UDP, TCP, ICMP, and IP packets are collected by the capture module and sent to a shared queue for processing. To assess the received data packets, the analysis and processing module compares them to a knowledge base and a predetermined set of criteria. The multi-threaded processes of the shared queue speed up NIDS. Good matching and evaluation allow for the identification of malicious packets and the generation of alarms. The reporting module generates alarm reports using data from the shared queue. The third-party service, which is keeping an eye on the entire scenario, alerts the user right away to the nature of the attack and provides the service provider with a consulting report (Shelke *et al.*, 2012). Although being a novel approach, the details of how it would be put into practice are not provided to support the idea.

Cross-site scripting (XSS) and DDoS attacks have been addressed by Shelke *et al.* (2012) using a multi-threaded NIDS. Three components make up the proposed NIDS, each of which serves a specific purpose. The UDP, TCP, ICMP, and IP packets are collected by the capture module and sent to a shared queue for processing. To assess the received data packets, the analysis and processing module compares them to a knowledge base and a predetermined set of criteria. The multi-threaded processes of the shared queue speed up NIDS. Good matching and assessment enable the detection of malicious packets and the warning generation. The reporting module produces alarm reports based on information from the shared queue. The third-party service, which is watching the whole situation, quickly alerts the user to the specifics of the attack and provides the service provider with a consulting report. The details of how it might be put into practice are not provided, even though it is an innovative approach.

According to research by Karande and Bhongade (2017) on hybrid intrusion detection systems for securing cloud-based services, the study makes use of an anomaly-based and signature-based intrusion detection and prevention system (IDS/IPS) together to form a hybrid intrusion detection system that is used to detect known attacks and vulnerabilities by signature-based systems and previously unknown attacks by anomaly-based systems, which are further strengthened by the addition of signatures. The learning of the system is done by conditional random field (CRF) (Karande & Bhongade, 2017). In this model, intrusion detection will be classified as signature-based, which matches the association rule with the packet feature to identify between a normal packet and a forged packet. The features of the Packet or network connection are extracted and compared with the Dataset which is built from a series of network captures of port 80 requests made to service during a period of 7 days. The traffic was captured with Wireshark. This tool is an open-source packet analyser that enables capturing live network packet data. Further characterisation is done by Anomaly-based detection where the trace log for the packet is generated which is in common log format and can be used by all readily available IDSs. The behaviour of a packet is monitored from a log which is labelled by learning with Conditional Random Field (CRF).

Using soft computing methods with conventional IDS in a cloud environment is helpful. Each approach does, however, have specific benefits and restrictions that have an impact on

IDS performance. This is summarised in Table 2.

Table 2. Intrusion detection system techniques

IDS Technique	Characteristics	Limitation
Signature-based detection	High detection reliability for known attacks.	High rate of false alarms for unidentified attackers.
	Matches collected patterns with a pre-configured knowledge base to determine intrusion.	Cannot recognise brand-new or modified assaults.
	Low cost of calculation.	Care should be taken when creating the knowledge base for matching.
Anomaly-based detection	A statistical test is applied to collected behaviour to detect incursion.	Attack detection takes a long time.
	Has the potential to reduce the number of false alarms for unidentified attacks.	The quantity of observed behaviour or features determines the accuracy of detection.
Hybrid detection techniques	It is a successful strategy for precisely classifying rules.	The cost of computation is substantial.

V. CONCLUSION

Cyberattacks are growing at an exponential rate, and there is no well-known method to stop all these attacks. Security has been a major challenge for cloud computing users because of the open and distributed architecture pattern of the cloud system. One of the most important approaches to reducing or stopping a cyberattack is intrusion detection systems (IDS). The implementation of an intrusion detection system has improved cloud security. It aids in ensuring the network's and data's confidentiality, integrity, and availability. A variety of intrusion detection techniques have been used to detect security threats that have evolved in cloud networks. The paper emphasises existing methods of IDS based on traditional techniques using soft computing. The review is then divided into sections based on the different types of cloud-based IDS, such as network-based IDS, host-based IDS, hypervisor-based IDS, and distributed intrusion detection systems, as well as different approaches for detecting an intrusion. Therefore, despite the advancement of numerous techniques and methods of detecting an intrusion in a cloud-based system, lots of loopholes still exist, making the cloud vulnerable to attacks and intrusion. It is therefore recommended that ensemble techniques be considered, which are used to decrease the variation of predictions and generalisation error when developing an intrusion detection system using any of the soft computing methods; this will therefore help to improve the detection rate and reduce false positives.

REFERENCES

- Ade, D. (2020). *Cloud computing and everything you need to know*. Trends, Web Design Tutorials and Articles. <https://ictacademy.com.ng/cloud-computing-and-everything-you-need-to-know/>
- Bahram, S., Jiang, X., Wang, Z., Grace, M., Li, J., Srinivasan, D., Rhee, J., & Xu, D. (2010). DKSM: Subverting virtual machine introspection for fun and profit. *29th IEEE Symposium on Reliable Distributed Systems*, 82–91. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SRDS.2010.39>
- Bakshi, A., & Dujodwala, Y. B. (2010). Securing cloud from DDOS attacks using intrusion detection system in virtual machine. *2nd International Conference on Communication Software and Networks (ICCSN)*, 260–264. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCSN.2010.56>
- Bharadwaja, S., Sun, W., Niamat, M., & Shen, F. (2011). Collabra: A xen hypervisor based collaborative intrusion detection system. *8th International Conference on Information Technology: New Generations (ITNG)*, 695–700. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ITNG.2011.123>
- Chaudhary, A. (2020). *Cloud security challenges in 2020*. Cloud Security Alliance. <https://cloudsecurityalliance.org/blog/2020/02/18/cloud-security-challenges-in-2020/>
- Chormale, A. A., & Ghatule, A. P. (2020). Cloud intrusion detection system using fuzzy clustering and artificial neural network. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1478(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1478/1/012030>
- Chung, C. J., Khatkar, P., Xing, T., Lee, J., & Huang, D. (2013). NICE: Network intrusion detection and countermeasure selection in virtual network systems. *IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing*, 10(4), 198–211. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TDSC.2013.8>
- Dinh, H. T., Lee, C., Niyato, D., & Ping, W. (2013). A survey of mobile cloud computing: architecture, applications, and approaches. *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*, 13(18), 1587–1611. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcm.1203>
- Doan, K., Lao, Y., Zhao, W., & Li, P. (2021). LIRA: Learnable, imperceptible and robust backdoor attacks. *IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV)*, 11966–11976. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCV48922.2021.01175>
- Elmasry, W., Akbulut, A., & Zaim, A. H. (2021). A design of an integrated cloud-based intrusion detection system with third party cloud service. *Open Computer Science*, 11(1), 365–379. <https://doi.org/10.1515/comp-2020-0214>
- Farsole, A. A., Kashikar, A. G., & Zunzunwala, A. (2010). Ethical hacking. *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 1(10), 14–20. <https://doi.org/10.5120/229-380>
- Gao, J. (2022). Network intrusion detection method combining CNN and BiLSTM in cloud computing environment. *Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience*, 2022(7272479), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/7272479>
- Goyal, P., Ribeiro, V. J., Saran, H., & Kumar, A. (2011). Strap-down Pedestrian Dead-Reckoning system. *2011 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, 1–7.

- <https://doi.org/10.1109/IPIN.2011.6071935>
- Gupta, S., Kumar, P., Sardana, A., & Abraham, A. (2012). A fingerprinting system calls approach for intrusion detection in a cloud environment. *4th International Conference on Computational Aspects of Social Networks (CASoN)*, 309–314. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CASoN.2012.6412420>
- Hashizume, K., Rosado, D. G., Fernández-Medina, E., & Fernandez, E. B. (2013). An analysis of security issues for cloud computing. *Journal of Internet Services and Applications*, 4(5), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1869-0238-4-5>
- Hsu, Y. F., He, Z. Y., Tarutani, Y., & Matsuoka, M. (2019). Toward an online network intrusion detection system based on ensemble learning. *IEEE 12th International Conference on Cloud Computing (CLOUD)*, 174–178. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CLOUD.2019.00037>
- Idhammad, M., Afdel, K., & Belouch, M. (2018). Distributed intrusion detection system for cloud environments based on data mining techniques. *Procedia Computer Science*, 127, 35–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2018.01.095>
- Jang-Jaccard, J., Nepal, S., & Guo, Y. J. (2013). Cybersecurity threats in cloud computing. *Journal of Telecommunications and the Digital Economy*, 1(1), 58–74. <https://doi.org/10.18080/jtde.v1n1.128>
- Jha, J., & Raha, L. (2013). Intrusion detection system using support vector machine. *International Journal of Applied Information Systems, ICWAC(3)*, 25–30. <https://doi.org/10.5120/icwac1342>
- Karande, S. C., & Bhongade, P. S. (2017). Hybrid intrusion detection system for securing cloud based services. *International Conference on Intelligent Computing and Applications*, 1–4.
- Kene, S. G., & Theng, D. P. (2015). A review on intrusion detection techniques for cloud computing and security challenges. *2nd International Conference on Electronics and Communication Systems (ICECS)*, 227–232. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ECS.2015.7124898>
- Khairkar, A. D., Kshirsagar, D. D., & Kumar, S. (2013). Ontology for detection of web attacks. *2013 International Conference on Communication Systems and Network Technologies (CSNT)*, 612–615. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CSNT.2013.131>
- King, S. T., Chen, P. M., Wang, Y. M., Verbowski, C., Wang, H. J., & Lorch, J. R. (2006). SubVirt: Implementing malware with virtual machines. *IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy*, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SP.2006.38>
- Kosamkar, V. B. (2016). Intrusion detection system in cloud computing: An overview. *International Journal on Recent and Innovation Trends in Computing and Communication*, 4(1), 164–167.
- Krishnan, R. (2017). *Security and privacy in cloud computing*. Master Thesis, Western Michigan University.
- Kumar, R., Kumar, P., Tripathi, R., Gupta, G. P., Garg, S., & Hassan, M. M. (2022). A distributed intrusion detection system to detect DDoS attacks in blockchain-enabled IoT network. *Journal of Parallel and Distributed Computing*, 164, 55–68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpdc.2022.01.030>
- Lata, S., & Singh, D. (2022). Intrusion detection system in cloud environment: Literature survey & future research directions. *International Journal of Information Management Data Insights*, 2(2), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jjime.2022.100134>
- Lee, J.-H., Park, M.-W., Eom, J.-H., & Chung, T.-M. (2011). Multi-level intrusion detection system and log management in cloud computing. *13th International Conference on Advanced Communication Technology (ICACT)*, 552–555.
- Li, Y., Jiang, Y., Li, Z., & Xia, S. T. (2022). Backdoor learning: A survey. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TNNLS.2022.3182979>
- Li, Y., Li, Y., Wu, B., Li, L., He, R., & Lyu, S. (2021). Invisible backdoor attack with sample-specific triggers. *IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV)*, 16463–16472. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCV48922.2021.01615>
- Liu, Z., Xu, B., Cheng, B., Hu, X., & Darbandi, M. (2022). Intrusion detection systems in the cloud computing: A comprehensive and deep literature review. *Concurrency and Computation: Practice and Experience*, 34(4), e6646. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cpe.6646>
- Lo, C. C., Huang, C. C., & Ku, J. (2010). A cooperative intrusion detection system framework for cloud computing networks. *39th International Conference on Parallel Processing Workshops*, 280–284. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICPPW.2010.46>
- Mansouri, N., Ghafari, R., & Zade, B. M. H. (2020). Cloud computing simulators: A comprehensive review. *Simulation Modelling Practice and Theory*, 104, 1–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.simpat.2020.102144>
- Mazzariello, C., Bifulco, R., & Canonico, R. (2010). Integrating a network IDS into an open source cloud computing environment. *Sixth International Conference on Information Assurance and Security*, 265–270. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISIAS.2010.5604069>
- Mehmood, Y., Shibli, M. A., Habiba, U., & Masood, R. (2013). Intrusion detection system in cloud computing: Challenges and opportunities. *2nd National Conference on Information Assurance (NCIA)*, 59–66. <https://doi.org/10.1109/NCIA.2013.6725325>
- Mell, P., & Grance, T. (2011). The NIST definition of cloud computing. In G. I. Nikolov (Ed.), *Cloud Computing and Government: Background, Benefits, Risks* (pp. 1–7). National Institute of Standards and Technology. <https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.SP.800-145>
- Mishra, V., Vijay, V. K., & Tazi, S. (2016). Intrusion detection system with snort in cloud computing: Advanced IDS. In S. C. Satapathy, A. Joshi, N. Modi, & N. Pathak (Eds.), *Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing* (Vol. 408, pp. 457–465). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-0129-1_48
- Modi, C. N., Patel, D. R., Patel, A., & Muttukrishnan, R. (2012). Bayesian classifier and snort based network intrusion detection system in cloud computing. *3rd International Conference on Computing, Communication and Networking Technologies (ICCCNT)*, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCCNT.2012.6396086>
- Modi, C., Patel, D., Borisaniya, B., Patel, H., Patel, A., & Rajarajan, M. (2013). A survey of intrusion detection techniques in Cloud. *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, 36(1), 42–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnca.2012.05.003>
- Mudzingwa, D., & Agrawal, R. (2012). A study of

- methodologies used in intrusion detection and prevention systems (IDPS). *IEEE Southeastcon*, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SECon.2012.6197080>
- Mukhopadhyay, R., & Nath, A. (2014). Ethical hacking: Scope and challenges in 21st century. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Advanced Engineering*, 1(11), 30–37.
- Nguyen, T. A., & Tran, T. A. (2020). Input-aware dynamic backdoor attack. In H. Larochelle, M. Ranzato, R. Hadsell, M. F. Balcan, & H. Lin (Eds.), *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* (Vol. 33, pp. 3454–3464). NeurIPS.
- Odun-Ayo, I., Ananya, M., Agono, F., & Goddy-Worlu, R. (2018). Cloud computing architecture: A critical analysis. *18th International Conference on Computational Science and Its Applications (ICCSA)*, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCSA.2018.8439638>
- Patel, A., Qassim, Q., Shukor, Z., Nogueira, J., Júnior, J., & Wills, C. (2010). Autonomic agent-based self-managed intrusion detection and prevention system. In N. Clarke, S. Furnell, & R. von Solms (Eds.), *South African Information Security Multi-Conference (SAISMC)* (pp. 223–234).
- Patil, S., Jangra, A., Bhale, M., Raina, A., & Kulkarni, P. (2018). Ethical hacking: The need for cyber security. *IEEE International Conference on Power, Control, Signals and Instrumentation Engineering (ICPCSI)*, 1602–1606. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICPCSI.2017.8391982>
- Rani, M., & Gagandeep. (2022). An efficient network intrusion detection system based on feature selection using evolutionary algorithm over balanced dataset. In N. Marriwala, C. Tripathi, S. Jain, & D. Kumar (Eds.), *Mobile Radio Communications and 5G Networks. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems* (Vol. 339, pp. 179–193). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-7018-3_15
- Sadiku, I. B., Ajayi, W., Sakpere, W., John-Dewole, T., & Badru, R. A. (2022). Effect of traditional and software-defined networking on performance of computer network. *Scientific Journal of Informatics*, 9(2), 111–122. <https://doi.org/10.15294/sji.v9i2.31315>
- Sakr, M. M., Tawfeeq, M. A., & El-Sisi, A. B. (2019). Network intrusion detection system based PSO-SVM for cloud computing. *International Journal of Computer Network and Information Security*, 11(3), 22–29. <https://doi.org/10.5815/ijcnis.2019.03.04>
- Saljoughi, A. S., Mehvarz, M., & Mirvaziri, H. (2017). Attacks and intrusion detection in cloud computing using neural networks and particle swarm optimization algorithms. *Emerging Science Journal*, 1(4), 179–191. <https://doi.org/10.28991/ijse-01120>
- Samreen, A., & Zaidi, F. B. (2012). Design and Development of Credit Scoring Model for the Commercial Banks of Pakistan: Forecasting Creditworthiness of Individual Borrowers. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 3(17), 155–166.
- Saraeian, S., & Golchi, M. M. (2020). Application of deep learning technique in an intrusion detection system. *International Journal of Computational Intelligence and Applications*, 19(2), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S1469026820500169>
- Shelke, P. K., Sontakke, S., & Gawande, A. D. (2012). Intrusion detection system for cloud computing. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, 1(4), 67–71.
- Srilatha, D., & Shyam, G. K. (2021). Cloud-based intrusion detection using kernel fuzzy clustering and optimal type-2 fuzzy neural network. *Cluster Computing*, 24(3), 2657–2672. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10586-021-03281-9>
- Sunyaev, A. (2020). Cloud Computing. In *Internet Computing* (pp. 195–236). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-34957-8_7
- Suthar, K. C. (2017). *Data security in cloud computing using encryption and obfuscation techniques*. PhD Thesis, Rai University.
- Thakur, K., Tao, L., Wang, T., & Ali, M. L. (2017). Cloud computing and its security issues. *Application and Theory of Computer Technology*, 2(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.22496/atct20161210>
- Vieira, K., Schulter, A., Westphall, C., & Westphall, C. M. (2010). Intrusion detection for grid and cloud computing. *IT Professional*, 12(4), 38–43. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MITP.2009.89>
- Zhu, Y., Gaba, G. S., Almansour, F. M., Alroobaea, R., & Masud, M. (2021). Application of data mining technology in detecting network intrusion and security maintenance. *Journal of Intelligent Systems*, 30(1), 664–676. <https://doi.org/10.1515/jisys-2020-0146>
- Zouhair, C., Abghour, N., Moussaid, K., El Omri, A., & Rida, M. (2018). A review of intrusion detection systems in cloud computing. In Y. Maleh, A. Ezzati, & M. Belaisaoui (Eds.), *Security and Privacy in Smart Sensor Networks* (pp. 253–283). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-5736-4.ch012>